

COMPONENTS OF DEVELOPING SYNONYMOUS THINKING IN STUDENTS AND ITS PEDAGOGICAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the relevance and theoretical foundations of the problem of healthy thinking, and highlights the content of the structural components of healthy thinking and healthy behavior, giving priority to the cognitive, preparatory, and final phases of the process of developing healthy thinking in future teachers. The article also provides information on the preliminary control results of experimental work and the specific characteristics of healthy thinking.

INTRODUCTION

In the development of world socio-economic relations, it is increasingly evident that human intelligence and spirituality are the main coordinating, developing factors and tools. This, in turn, makes the problem of educating high-level specialists, pedagogical personnel capable of working together in a competitive and innovative educational environment in the labor market even more urgent.

In New Uzbekistan, which has chosen the path of development from national revival to national advancement, the main strategic tasks are to modernize the country, improve the quality of training highly qualified personnel for sustainable socio-economic development, develop human capital based on the requirements of the labor market, introduce digital technologies and modern methods into the educational process, train highly qualified, creative and systematic thinking personnel, able to make independent decisions based on international standards, create the necessary conditions for their manifestation of intellectual abilities and formation as spiritually mature individuals [1]. In this regard, improving the mechanisms that serve to improve the quality of training qualified specialists in higher educational institutions is an urgent problem. The international program for training future pedagogical personnel has identified the development of tactics for developing student activities focused on the "reflective practitioner" [2] and the improvement of pedagogical mechanisms to ensure the harmony of creative and rational approaches as an important task.

Research objective.

Based on the tasks set out in the legal and regulatory documents on the training of qualified teaching staff in our republic and the requirements of the international program for the training of future pedagogical personnel, the main goal of the research was to develop sanogeneous thinking in future teachers, to introduce reflexive and integrative approaches by

ensuring interdisciplinary integration in this process, to clarify the pedagogical conditions for the development of sanogeneous thinking, and to reveal its essence as a pedagogical phenomenon from the point of view of modern reality, to identify its components and pedagogical psychological characteristics.

Literature analysis.

The problem of sanogeneous thinking has been studied by our country and a number of foreign scientists. [4,5,6,8,9,12,15,18]. They mainly pay special attention to studying the essence, nature of sanogeneous thinking and the mechanisms of its development. In these scientific research works, mainly the theoretical-philosophical, social and psychological aspects of the problem have been widely studied. In their works, the authors pay attention to individual forms of sanogenic thinking, to specific methods of forming its elements.

A person must control his behavior, feelings, mood in the process of social relations. To do this, he must understand himself more deeply. Each person must be able to control not only his feelings and behavior, but also his way of thinking in accordance with certain rules.

In this regard, pedagogical and psychological scientists distinguish two types of thinking: sanogenic and pathogenic thinking.

Sanogenic thinking (from Latin: "sanus" - healthy and from Greek - "genesis" - development) is thinking that controls feelings, inner experiences, thoughts and emotions, and makes them healthy.

Pathogenic thinking is a set of negative views that harm a person's health, which is explained by emotional instability and internal conflicts that arise in the process of a person's self- and interpersonal relationships. Professor Yu.M. Orlov, who developed the theoretical and practical foundations of sanogenic thinking, touches on the issue of human mental health and expresses the following opinion: "Sanogenic thinking is one of the most reliable ways of philosophy of life, health of mind and body. This methodology allows you to master new emotional-mental habits at a high level, accumulates the experience of past pathogenic thinking. Sanogenic thinking is an effective method of improving the health of the human mind. That is, a method of eliminating crisis situations that arise during a person's life activity with the help of spiritual support, through emotional-emotional self-influence" [3, p. 19]. Continuing her reasoning, the scientist firmly emphasizes the following points: she believes that the main importance of healthy thinking is to create conditions for achieving the goals of self-improvement, that is, harmony of character, harmony with oneself and others, as well as eliminating bad habits, managing one's emotions, and controlling one's needs. S. Atakhanova, studying the problem of healthy thinking, expresses the following opinion: "Healthy thinking is associated with a person's mental and emotional activities, and if it is directed towards healthy thinking, healthy thinking is formed. Mental activity is the task of acquiring existing knowledge and skills, and emotional activity means an emotional attitude towards a healthy life [4, 5 p.]. Although the author reveals the psychological, pedagogical, and philosophical content of the concept of healthy thinking, he does not clearly distinguish its structural components.

The scientist L.A. Kananchuk, who studied the problem of positive reflection, concludes: the inability of people to act correctly in a certain way in the process of social interaction, discrepancies between the expected and actual actions of subjects and in understanding each other, cause serious difficulties. In our opinion, such difficulties can be eliminated through positive reflection [10, p. 4].

One of the researchers who studied the problem of positive thinking in connection with the reflexive abilities of a person is N.V. Pavlyuchenkova. Positive reflection is a factor affecting personal development, adaptability and control of negative emotional states, it is the ability of a person to cope with difficult life situations [11, p. 22].

N.V. Pil suggests using positive thinking as a way to overcome failure, achieve confidence, success and happiness. He offers his famous formula of optimism, which has been used by many people who have adopted it as a simple and effective philosophy of their lives [12, 89 p.].

Anna Hilman, studying the problem of sanogenous thinking, evaluates this way of thinking as a tool for students to develop their own mental state, self-regulation and the right guidelines for future professional pedagogical activities [13, 12 p.]. O.Yu. Osadko and I.F. Arshavas recognize that the physical, psychological health and effective social adaptation of a person depend on his potential for sanogenous thinking [14, 45 p., 15, 18 p.], while S. Maddi believes that sanogenous thinking ensures the achievement of mental and spiritual health [16].

When analyzed pedagogically, the concept of sanogenic thinking is based on the thesis of the priority of cognitive assessments over pedagogical problems and emotional experiences arising in connection with the educational process, which is the process of acquiring skills related to constructive methods of solving problems related to pedagogical activity by using the student's thoughts to influence emotions and changing cognitive assessments. Based on the author's approach, we can say that "sanogenic thinking" is a process of understanding the content of the events and reflecting emotional experiences of the student, observing them at a high level and monitoring them individually. Also, sanogenic thinking reflects a set of mental activity skills related to positive thinking and creative abilities of students [17, p. 75].

The separation of such structural components as factors determining healthy thinking and healthy behavior in future teachers is associated with the creation (organization) of the necessary social environment that ensures the development of the future teacher's personality, favorable conditions for the effective conduct of educational, scientific research and practical activities in connection with the educational process, and the establishment of a conscious attitude towards self-development.

Based on the considerations and definitions given on healthy thinking, the following specific pedagogical and psychological characteristics were distinguished:

- The ability to express one's thoughts externally, that is, the manifestation of exteriorization;
- The manifestation of interiorization (internal acceptance) in the thinking process;
- Unusualness (improvisation) and creativity in thinking;
- Reflexivity of thinking and positive thinking;
- Manifestation of personal reflection and independence in thinking;
- Harmonious implementation of mental actions (hearing, speech and movement);
- Flexibility in thinking;
- High self-confidence and control in the thinking process;
- Harmony of emotionality and intellectual approach in the thinking process.

CONCLUSION AND PRACTICAL SUGGESTIONS

The theoretical understanding of the problem of developing healthy thinking in future teachers is currently being rapidly implemented. From a traditional point of view, the content of healthy thinking is explained by healthy thinking, the positive orientation of human thinking.

In modern studies, healthy thinking is considered in connection with controlling negative emotional experiences in a person, ensuring his health, increasing the effectiveness of educational activities, and personal reflexive skills.

Based on prioritizing the cognitive, preparatory, and final phases of the process of developing healthy thinking in future teachers, the motivational, reflexive, operational skills of healthy thinking and the structural components of healthy behavior, such as orientation, emotional stability, and meaningfulness, were explained.

In connection with the development of healthy thinking in future teachers, such pedagogical and psychological characteristics as the ability to express thoughts externally, interiorization in the thinking process, manifestation of personal reflection and independence, flexibility in thinking, self-confidence, high control, harmony of emotionality and mental approaches were highlighted. Healthy (healthy) thinking is one of the unconventional methods of protecting human health, ensuring the formation of new thinking skills. Also, healthy thinking skills allow you to master various ways of thinking, give it freedom, and reduce the excessive manifestation of emotions. In order to master healthy thinking skills, a person must first cultivate new thinking about specific emotional states (for example, hatred, shame, failure, insecurity, inadequate assessment, and negative thoughts) that he experiences. Only then will a person get rid of certain stereotyped thoughts and behavioral skills that he has. In this regard, it is appropriate to take into account the pedagogical and psychological characteristics of students in developing their sanogenic thinking and to use reflexive technologies in this process.

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